

Synthesis of New 3-Aminoacetyl Carbamide-4-Thiazolidones and Their Fungicidal Properties

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Various 3-aminoacetyl carbamide-4-thiazolidones(IV) were synthesized by the reaction of mercaptoacetic acid with arylidene-1-(hydrazoacetyl)-3-substituted carbamides(III).

THIAZOLIDONE derivatives exhibit a variety of pharmacological activities¹⁻⁴. The presence of N-C-S linkages has been postulated to account for the antifungal activity of 4-thiazolidones⁵. Attempts have been made earlier to enhance the fungitoxicity of thiazolidone derivatives by introducing different substituents either at 2, 3 or 5 position in the thiazolidone ring⁶⁻¹⁰.

These observations prompted the synthesis of various 3-aminoacetyl carbamide-4-thiazolidones (Fig. 1) in order to ascertain the effect of substituted acetyl carbamides attached to the 3-position of the 4-thiazolidones on fungitoxicity. 1-(Hydrazoacetyl)-3-substituted carbamides(II) were obtained

by the reaction of hydrazine hydrate with chloroacetyl carbamides(I). Condensation of (II) with aromatic aldehydes in glacial acetic acid furnished arylidene-1-(hydrazoacetyl)-3-substituted carbamides(III), and the structure of these compounds was established by their analytical data and i.r. spectral data which showed absorption bands at 3200-3300 cm⁻¹ (N-H stretching), 1610-1665 cm⁻¹ (CONH, C=N), 1490-1540 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretching) and 750-875 cm⁻¹ (monosubstituted benzene). Reaction of (III) with mercaptoacetic acid in dry dioxan yielded 3-aminoacetyl carbamide-4-thiazolidones(IV). The i.r. spectra of these compounds showed bands at 1650-1685 cm⁻¹ (ring C=O), 1600-1610 cm⁻¹ (CONH, C=C aromatic), 1420-1520 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretching), 1250-1310 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C) and 745-820 cm⁻¹ (substituted benzene).

Experimental

Infrared spectra was obtained in KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected.

Chloroacetyl carbamides(I) were synthesised by the methods reported earlier¹¹⁻¹⁴.

1-Hydrazoacetyl-3-substituted carbamides(II₁₋₅):

Hydrazine hydrate 99% (0.15 mole) was added to the solution of appropriate chloroacetyl carbamides (I, 0.15 mole) in absolute ethanol and the resulting mixture was heated under reflux for 6-8 hrs. A solid separating from the refluxing solution was filtered off after the solution had cooled and crystallized from ethanol to yield II (R = C₆H₅) - m.p. 149-50°, yield 60%, (Found: C, 51.82; H, 5.03; N, 26.73%. Calcd. for C₉H₁₂N₄O₂: C, 51.92; H, 5.77; N, 26.92%). II (R = o-CH₃C₆H₄) - m.p. 171-72°, yield 58%, (Found: C, 54.32; H, 6.08; N, 25.25%. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₄N₄O₂: C, 54.05; H, 6.30; N, 25.22%), II (R = m-CH₃C₆H₄) - m.p., 280-82°; yield 50%, (Found: C, 54.29; H, 6.05; N, 25.38%, Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₄N₄O₂: C, 54.05; H,

Fig. 1

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6.31 ; N, 25.22%), II (R=*p*-CH₃C₆H₄)—m. p., 165 ; yield, 65%, (Found : C, 54.00 ; H, 6.70 ; N, 25.00%, Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₄N₄O₂ : C, 54.05 ; H, 6.31 ; N, 25.22%) and II (R= α -C₁₀H₇)—m.p., 149-51° ; yield, 10%, (Found : C, 60.06 ; H, 5.33 ; N, 21.44%. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄N₄O₂ : C, 60.46 ; H, 5.81 ; N, 21.74%).

Arylidene-1-(hydrazoacetyl)-3-substituted carbamides(III) :

A mixture of (II, 0.01 mole) and a suitable aldehyde (0.01 mole) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 5-6 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice cold water and the product, which precipitated out was collected by filtration, washed several times with water and then crystallised from ethanol and ethanol-water. Compounds synthesized are recorded in Table 1. All the compounds showed consistent elemental analyses.

TABLE 1—ARYLIDENE-1-(HYDRAZOACETYL)-3-SUBSTITUTED CARBAMIDES(III)

Compd.* No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.F. °C
	R=C ₆ H ₅			
1.	H	H	H	100-01
2.	H	H	CH ₃	93-5
3.	OH	H	H	200-01
4.	H	H	NO ₂	141-2
5.	H	OCH ₃	OH	120
	R= <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄			
6.	H	H	H	127-28
7.	H	H	CH ₃	85-87
8.	OH	H	H	77-78
9.	H	H	NO ₂	121
10.	H	OCH ₃	OH	87
	R= <i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄			
11.	H	H	H	105-6
12.	H	H	CH ₃	117
13.	H	H	NO ₂	139-40
14.	H	OCH ₃	OH	131-32
	R= <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄			
15.	H	H	H	111-12
16.	H	H	CH ₃	122
17.	OH	H	H	85
18.	H	H	NO ₂	228
19.	H	OCH ₃	OH	220
	R= α -C ₁₀ H ₇			
20.	H	H	H	195-7
21.	H	H	Cl	185
22.	OH	H	H	121
23.	H	H	NO ₂	194
24.	H	OCH ₃	OH	191-2

* yields varied between 55-70%.

3-Aminoacetyl carbamide-4-thiazolidones(IV) :

Mercaptoacetic acid (0.015 mole) was added to a well stirred solution of (III, 0.05 mole) in 50 ml dry dioxan. The mixture was refluxed for 3-4 hrs. The

excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure. On cooling, the solid mass which separated out was washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution and finally recrystallised from the proper solvent. The melting points and analytical data of these compounds are recorded in Table 2. All the compounds showed consistent elemental analyses.

TABLE 2—3-AMINOACETYL CARBAMIDE-4-THIAZOLIDONES(IV)

Compd.* No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Solvent of crystallization	M.P. °C
	R=C ₆ H ₅				
1.	H	H	H	a	182-83
2.	H	H	CH ₃	b	152
3.	OH	H	H	c	154-56
4.	H	H	NO ₂	b	122
5.	H	OCH ₃	OH	a	145-46
	R= <i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄				
6.	H	H	H	b	280d
7.	H	H	CH ₃	a	180
8.	OH	H	H	a	153-54
9.	H	H	NO ₂	b	202-3
10.	H	OCH ₃	OH	b	168
	R= <i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄				
11.	H	H	H	c	181-82
12.	H	H	CH ₃	b	163
13.	H	H	NO ₂	c	135
14.	H	OCH ₃	OH	b	136
	R= <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄				
15.	H	H	H	b	136-37
16.	H	H	CH ₃	a	238
17.	OH	H	H	c	125
18.	H	H	NO ₂	c	235-36
19.	H	OCH ₃	OH	a	250
	R= α -C ₁₀ H ₇				
20.	H	H	H	c	165-66
21.	H	H	CH ₃	c	200
22.	OH	H	H	c	170
23.	H	H	NO ₂	c	209-10
24.	H	OCH ₃	OH	a	202-3

* Yields ranged between 40-65%. a, Alcohol-water, b, Alcohol, c, Dioxan.

Fungicidal activity :

The compounds recorded in Table 2 were screened for their antifungal activity against *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Fusarium equiseti* at concentrations 2 and 0.2% (W/V) by Paper-disc plate method¹⁵. None of the compounds exhibited significant antifungal activity against any of the test fungi at any of the test concentrations.

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